

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE ESTIMATION OF VILDAGLIPTIN IN BULK AND ITS DOSAGE FORM USING UV SPECTROPHOTOMETER

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 11/12/2017

Available online

01/01/2018

Keywords

Vildagliptin,
Method Validation,
Spectrophotometric.

ABSTRACT

A simple, rapid, precise and economical Analytical method development has been developed for quantitative vildagliptin in manufactured tablet formulation. The stock solution and subsequent dilution of vildagliptin was done in 0.1% NaOH. Solution of vildagliptin in 0.1% NaOH showed absorption maxima at 216.00 nm. The drug obeyed Beers-Lamberts Law in the concentration range of 10-100 µg/mL with Coefficient of correlation (R²) was 0.997. The standard the method can be adopted in routine analysis of vildagliptin in bulk and tablet dosage form.

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Please cite this article in press as **P.V. Prasad et al.** Analytical Method Development and Validation for the Estimation of Vildagliptin in Bulk and its Dosage Form Using UV Spectrophotometer. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(12).

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INTRODUCTION

Vildagliptin, a member of the class that enhances islet cell insulin secretion via an augmented incretin effect, is a high affinity dipeptidyl-peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitor that improves glycaemic control. The administration of vildagliptin results in rapid and near-complete inhibition of DPP-4 activity. Vildagliptin shows weak inhibition of, and rapid dissociation from DPP-8 and DPP-9, compared to DPP-4. In patients with type 2 diabetes, administration of vildagliptin led to inhibition of DPP-4 enzyme activity for a 24-hour period. Vildagliptin inhibition of DPP-4 results in increased fasting and postprandial endogenous levels of the incretin hormones GLP-1 (glucagon-like peptide 1) and GIP (glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptide). The degree of improvement in beta-cell function is dependent on the initial degree of impairment; in non-diabetic (normal glycaemic) individuals, vildagliptin does not stimulate insulin secretion or reduce glucose levels. By increasing endogenous GLP-1 levels, vildagliptin enhances the sensitivity of alpha cells to glucose, resulting in reduced glucagon secretion. There is a reduction in inappropriate glucagon release during meals. The increase in the insulin/glucagon ratio with hyperglycaemia, due to increased incretin hormone levels, may thus be expected to decrease postprandial hepatic glucose production, leading to reduced glycaemia. The known effect of increased GLP-1 levels to delay gastric emptying is not observed with vildagliptin treatment.

Molecular Formula	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂
Molecular mass	303.399 g/mol
Chemical name	(S)-1-[N-(3-hydroxy-1-adamantyl)glycyl]pyrrolidine-2-carbonitrile
Trademarks	Galvus (Novartis), Galvusmet, Jalra , Jalra-M, Zomelis , Zomelis-Met
Generic names	Vildagliptin

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Drug sample:

Vildagliptin was obtained from Pfizer pharmaceutical Pvt. Ltd, Chennai.

Chemical & reagents:

NaOH, H₂O₂, HCl, Ethanol are obtained from SD fine-Chem labs, Hyderabad. Distilled water was prepared in house.

Apparatus:

A Shimadzu 1800 version 1.12-Double Beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer. UV spectra of standard and sample solutions were recorded in 1 cm quartz cells at the wavelength ranges of 200-400nm.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT

An UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer with 1cm matched quartz cells were used for the spectral and absorbance measurements. Sonicator was used for sonication. All the chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade and the aqueous solutions were freshly prepared with distilled water.

Solubility Studies

Vildagliptin was tested in various solvents like sodium hydroxide, water, acetic acid, hydrochloric acid. Vildagliptin was found to be soluble in sodium hydroxide. Vildagliptin was easily soluble at room temperature.

λ Max determination

We can prepare working concentrations from stock solution by using sodium hydroxide. The stock solution is diluted to prepare 25,50 and 75µg/ml solutions and scanned in the UV range 200 to 400 nm and the absorbance values are noted. Based on these absorbance values the λ max was determined. The wavelength at which maximum concentration takes place was noted.

Preparation of stock solution

1mg/ml Vildagliptin solution was prepared by dissolving 100mg of vildagliptin in 100ml 0.1N NaOH. Working standard solutions were prepared by dissolving 0.5ml in 10ml of NaOH and it is 50 microgram per ml

Dosage form preparation

3.98mg of Vildagliptin and dissolve in 100ml of sodium hydroxide. From the above, 0.5ml solution was taken and made up to final volume of 10ml with sodium hydroxide and it is 50 microgram per ml.

VALIDATION

The proposed method was validated for the following parameters as per ICH.

Accuracy
Precision
Linearity
Limit of detection
Limit of quantification
Robustness
Degradation studies
Assay

ACCURACY

Accuracy refers to the closeness of measurement to the true value. Accuracy is also defined as the extent to which a given measurement agrees with the standard value for that measurement. A method is said to be accurate if it gives the correct numerical answer for the analyte. Scientists often report percent error of a measurement, which expresses how far a measured value is from the true value.

For example, different types of glassware used in the lab are inherently different in their level of accuracy. If you use an unmarked flask to try to obtain 1 liter of liquid, you are likely not going to be very accurate. If you use a 1 liter beaker, you will probably be accurate within several milliliters. If you use a volumetric flask, the accuracy of the measurement may be within a milliliter or two.

Method

Accuracy is performed by diluting the stock solution in three different concentrations at 50%, 100% and 150%. Six samples was prepared from 50% concentration, three samples was prepared from 100% concentration and another six samples from 150% concentration. All the samples were scanned at respective λ max in photometric mode and the absorbance of each sample was noted. Then Percentage recovery and mean percentage recovery are calculated. The accuracy parameter calculated by using this formula;

$$\text{Amount added} = \text{sample weight} \times \text{average assay} \times \text{label claim} \times 1000/\text{sample dilution} \times 100 \times \text{average weight}$$

$$\text{Amount found} = \text{sample absorbance} \times \text{standard weight} \times \text{standard potency} \times 1000/\text{standard absorbance} \times \text{standard dilution} \times 100$$

$$\% \text{ Recovery} = \text{amount found}/\text{amount added} \times 100$$

PRECISION

Precision refers to the closeness of two or more measurements to each other. Precision is the reproducibility of multiple measurements. It is usually described by the standard deviation, standard error or confidence interval. For example, if you weigh a given substance five times and get the same result each time, then your measurement is very precise. Precision may consists of repeatability, intermediate precision and reproducibility.

Method

Precision is performed in which the stock solution is diluted in optimum concentration of six samples. The six samples were scanned at respective λ max and their absorbance was note. According to ICH, precision should be performed at two different levels. They are repeatability and intermediate precision. Repeatability is the variation arising when all efforts are made to keep conditions constant by using the same instrument and operator and repeating during a short time period. Intermediate precision (also called within-laboratory or within device) is a measure of precision under a defined set of conditions: same measurement procedure, same measuring system, same location, and replicate measurements on the same or similar objects over an extended period of time. In this method, precision was performed by determining the absorbance of six samples. The resulting data are tabulated by the absorbance of inter day and intraday. Mean, standard deviation and percentage relative standard deviation are calculated. The precision parameter calculated by using this formula;

$$\% \text{ assay} = \text{Absorbance in sample} \times \text{weight of standard} \times \text{dilution of standard} \times \text{average weight} \times 100/\text{Absorbance in standard} \times \text{dilution of standard} \times \text{weight of sample} \times \text{label claim}$$

$$\% \text{ relative standard deviation} = \text{standard deviation}/\text{mean} \times 100$$

LINEARITY

Linearity is the property of a mathematical relationship or function which means that it can be graphically represented as a straight line. Linearity expresses that concentration is directly proportional to absorbance. Examples are the relationship of voltage and current across a resistor (ohm's law) or the mass and weight of an object.

Method

Linearity was determined by preparing 5 samples of different concentrations of vildagliptin in bulk (pure drug). The concentrations are 10, 27.5, 50, 75 and 100µg/ml. These concentrations are taken from the stock solution and diluted to final volume with sodium hydroxide. These concentrations are scanned at respective λ max in photometric mode and the absorbance was noted for each concentration. The calibration curve is plotted by taking concentration on x-axis and absorbance on y-axis. The correlation coefficient and slope are calculated.

LIMIT OF DETECTION (LOD):

Detection limit or limit of detection is the lowest quantity of a substance that can be distinguished from the absence of that substance (a blank value) within a stated confidence limit (generally 1%). The detection limit is estimated from the mean of the blank, the standard deviation of the blank and some confidence factor. Other considerations that affects the detection limit is the accuracy of the model used to predict concentration from the raw analytical signal.

Method

Limit of detection is processed by preparing very dilute concentrations like 0.1, 0.2, 0.5...up to 10µg/ml and scanned at respective λ max, where the concentration shows the detectable absorbance.

The LOD calculated by using this formula; Limit of detection (LOD) = $3 \times$ standard deviation/slope

LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION:

Limit of quantification is the lowest concentration at which the analyte cannot only be reliably detected but at which some predefined goals for bias and imprecision are met. The LOQ may be equivalent to the LOD or it could be at a much higher concentration.

Method

Limit of quantification is processed by preparing very dilute concentrations like 0.1, 0.2, 0.5..... up to 10µg/ml and scanned at respective λ max, where the concentration shows the quantified absorbance.

The LOQ calculated by using this formula; Limit of quantification (LOQ) = $10 \times$ standard deviation/slope

ROBUSTNESS:

Robustness was evaluated by making some small changes in the method like changing the λ max and the concentration of the solvent. As the λ max changes to 214 nm, 218 nm and solvent to 0.09N, 0.2N NaOH the result obtained was found to have good absorbance. The percentage assay was found to be 99.32% and the values are given in the table.

DEGRADATION STUDIES

It is also known as forced degradation studies or stability studies. In this method the drug has undergone different chemical studies and environmental conditions. Degradation studies was checked by subjecting the dosage form sample to acid, hydrogen peroxide, Ultra violet cabinet region and the drug exposed to sunlight.

ASSAY:

The percentage purity was determined for vildagliptin in its dosage form and the results obtained are accurate and precise. The percentage assay was found to be 100.68%.

Assay = Absorbance in sample/absorbance in standard \times weight of standard/dilution of standard \times dilution of sample/weight of sample \times average weight/label claim \times 100

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Graph 1: Vildagliptin of bulk drug.

The λ max of vildagliptin bulk drug found to be 216 nm

Graph 2: Vildagliptin of dosage form.

The λ max of vildagliptin dosage form found to be 216 nm

Table 1: SOLUBILITY PROFILE OF VILDAGLIPTIN IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS.

S.NO	SOLVENTS	CATEGORY
1	Distilled water	Very soluble
2	0.1% of NaOH	Freely soluble
3	0.1% Hcl	Freely soluble
4	Ethanol	Excellent
5	Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)	Soluble
6	Dimethyl formamide (DMF)	Soluble
7	n-butanol	Less soluble

Table 2: LINEARITY OF VILDAGLIPTIN.

S. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
1	10	0.1
2	27.5	0.235
3	50	0.425
4	75	0.612
5	100	0.806

Graph 3: LINEARITY CURVE OF VILDAGLIPTIN.**Table 3: PRECISION OF VILDAGLIPTIN.**

S. NO	INTRA DAY		INTER DAY	
	Absorbance	% Assay	Absorbance	% Assay
1	0.450	101.81	0.445	100.68
2	0.445	100.68	0.445	100.68
3	0.442	100.00	0.442	100.00
4	0.448	101.36	0.449	101.58
5	0.440	99.55	0.440	99.55
6	0.445	100.68	0.446	100.90
Average	0.445	100.68	0.44	100.57
STD DEV	0.004	0.834	0.003	0.712
% RSD	0.829	0.829	0.708	0.708

Table 4: ACCURACY OF VILDAGLIPTIN.

S. No	Accuracy Level	Wt. of the sample	Sample Abs	Amount Added	Amount Found	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
1	5050	199.43	0.222	25.16	25.11	99.83	100.58
2		199.43	0.227	25.16	25.68	102.08	
3		199.43	0.225	25.16	25.45	101.18	
4	50	199.43	0.225	25.16	25.45	101.18	99.46
5		199.43	0.225	25.16	25.45	101.18	
6		199.43	0.218	25.16	24.66	98.03	
7	100	398.86	0.441	50.31	49.89	99.16	100.13
8		398.86	0.442	50.31	50.00	99.38	
9		398.86	0.444	50.31	50.23	99.83	
10	150	598.29	0.665	75.47	75.23	99.68	101.63
11		598.29	0.665	75.47	75.23	99.68	
12		598.29	0.655	75.47	74.10	98.18	
13		598.29	0.683	75.47	77.26	102.38	
14		598.29	0.678	75.47	76.70	101.63	

Table 5: ROBUSTNESS OF VILDAGLIPTIN.

S. No	Change in Condition	Absorbance	% Assay
1	214 nm	0.438	99.10
2	216 nm	0.439	99.32
3	218 nm	0.443	100.23
4	0.09 N NaOH	0.436	98.64
5	0.1 N NaOH	0.439	99.32
6	0.2 N NaOH	0.434	98.19

Table 6: DEGRADATION STUDIES OF VILDAGLIPTIN.

S. No	Stress Condition	Absorption of Sample	% Assay	Difference in Assay
1	0.1 N HCl	0.485	109.73	9.73
2	3% H ₂ O ₂	0.453	102.49	2.49
3	Sun Light	0.475	107.47	7.47
4	UV Light	0.426	96.38	-3.62
5	Water	0.44	99.55	-0.45

Table 7 ASSAY OF VILDAGLIPTIN.

S. No	Absorbance	% Assay
1	0.45	101.81
2	0.445	100.68
3	0.442	100.00
4	0.448	101.36
5	0.44	99.55
6	0.445	100.68
Average	0.445	100.68
STD DEV	0.0037	0.8343
% RSD	0.83	0.83

CONCLUSION

In this proposal method the linearity was observed in the concentration range of 10 – 100 µg/ml with correlation co-efficient (r^2) 0.9974 for vildagliptin at 216 nm the results of analysis of pharmaceutical formulation by the proposed method was highly reproducible and reliable. The method can be used for routine analysis for determination of vildagliptin in bulk and formulation. From the results, it was found that the developed UV method was found to be simple, sensitive, accurate, precise, specific, and rapid. The method can be applied for routine analysis of pure and formulation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

It gives me profound pleasure to express my deep sense of gratitude and indebtedness to revered research Dr. Mohammed Ishaq, M. Pharm., Ph.D., Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis.

REFERENCE

1. Ebenesan P, Jainu M. Vildagliptin and Insulin Combinatorial Therapy Drug Safety Monitoring in Diabetic Rats. Indian J of Pharmaceutical Education and Research. 2017, 51(1), 150-55.
2. G. R. Chatwal, Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Introduction to Pharmaceutical Analysis, Himalaya Publishing House, vol-1, 1995, 1-3
3. R. A. Day, A. L. Underwood, Quantitative Analysis, Spectrophotometry, Prentice-Hall of India Private Limited, 1991, 388-417.
4. P. Parimo, Pharmaceutical Analysis, Introduction to Pharmaceutical Analysis, CBS Publishers and Distributors, 1998, 1-10.
5. P. S. Kalsi, Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds, Ultraviolet and Visible Spectroscopy, New Age International (P) Limited, Publishers, 2002, 9-19.
6. G. Devala Rao, Pharmaceutical Analysis, Introduction to Spectrophotometry, Birla Publications Pvt. Ltd, vol-2, 2002, 5-19.
7. Khushabu R. Patil, Dr. Tushar deshमुख, Dr. Vijay R. Patil, Development and Validation of HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Vildagliptin and Metformin in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form, World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 4(09), 2015, 1151-1162.
8. Banik S, Karmakar P, MAH Miah, Development and Validation of a UV spectrophotometric method for determination of Vildagliptin and Linagliptin in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form, Bangladesh Pharmaceutical Journal 18(2), 2015, 163-168.
9. Praveenkumar Ramachandra, Mahalingam Vasudevan, Deecaraman, Ravandur Shivanna Chandan, Development and validation of Vildagliptin by using RP-HPLC, World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 3(2), 2013, 2126-2132.
10. Baokar Shrikrishna, Mulgund SV and Ranpise NS, Simultaneous spectrophotometric estimation of Vildagliptin and Metformin by using RP-HPLC, Research Journal of Pharmaceutical Dosage forms and Technology, 5(2), 2013, 95-98.

11. Sultana, Razia; Bachar, Sitesh C.; Rahman, Fatema, Development and Validation of Stability indicating assay method of Vildagliptin in bulk and tablet dosage form by RP-HPLC, International Journal of Pharmacy and Life Sciences, 4(4), 2013, 2530-2534.
12. Santhakumari B, Pharne AB, Ghemud AS, Jain HK, Kulkarni MJ, Bioanalytical method development and validation of Vildagliptin by using RP-HPLC method, International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 4(3), 2011, 119-123.
13. ICH harmonized tripartite guideline, validation of analytical procedures: text and methodology, Q2R1, International Conference on Harmonization of Technical requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human use, 2005.
14. Ola Mahmoud Younes, Joumaa-Zehouri, HabibAbboud, Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Vildagliptin in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms, International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research, 29(1), 2014, 33-36.
15. Subhakar Nandipati, Development and Validation of RP-HPLC method for Simultaneous Determination of Vildagliptin and Metformin in Bulk and Formulation Dosage, 2(3), 2012, 44-50.

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